

Surface Tensions of Binary Solutions

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The results from an extensive work carried out for the experimental verification of the equation $V_m r_m^2 = K_1 x + K_2$ put forth earlier have been presented. In this equation V_m is mean molecular volume of the solution, r_m is surface tension of the solution, x is molar fraction of the solute and K_1 and K_2 are constants. The equation is found to be fairly and widely applicable in the case of following types of binary systems; (i) Electrolytes in water, (ii) Electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents at low and high concentration ranges, (iii) organic solids in organic solvents at low and high concentration ranges, (iv) organic liquids in organic solvents having large and small, mutual surface tension differences at all concentration ranges.

ALTHOUGH an extensive work¹ has been carried out to correlate surface tensions of binary solutions and their concentrations, no relationship of simple nature and wide applicability is available. An attempt, was therefore, made^{2,3} by us to obtain an equation applicable to various types of binary systems, and the following relationship was derived from the considerations of Hammic and Andrew's⁴ mixture law equations :

$$V_m r_m^2 = K_1 X + K_2$$

where r_m = Surface tension of the solution

X = mole fraction of solute.

K_1 and K_2 are constants, depending on parachor values of solute and solvent.

V_m = Mean molecular volume of the solution and is given by $V_m = M_m/d_m$; d_m is the density of the solution and M_m is mean molecular weight of the system given by $M_m = M_1 X_1 + (1-x)M_2$; M_1 and M_2 being respectively the molecular weights of solute and the solvent.

In the present paper the representative results from an extensive work carried out for the experimental verification of the foregoing equation have been presented.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of B.D.H. or A.R. quality where purity was checked using standard methods.

Jaeger's maximum bubble pressure method was used to determine surface tensions. 'r' the radius of the capillary was determined using a high powered microscope having a micrometer eyepiece of accuracy 10⁻⁷ cms. Only significant figures (i.e., r up to 0.0001 cms.) were retained. This radius value tallied with the radius value calculated by using back calculation method.

All experimental solutions were thermostated at 25° ± 0.10° using water thermostat having a JUMO—magnetic relay and contact thermometer etc. in the circuit.

The apparatus was standardised by finding surface tensions of pure liquids which agreed well with the standard values in the literature.

Other details can be found elsewhere.^{2,3,6}

Results

Meanings of the notations used in the following tables have been given under 'Introduction'.

TABLE 1—POTASSIUM DI-HYDROGEN PHOSPHATE IN WATER

$X \times 10^2$	d_m	M_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.9458	1.052	19.14	78.02	54.13
0.7082	1.035	18.86	75.45	53.74
0.5145	1.023	18.64	73.91	53.43
0.3098	1.013	18.39	73.16	53.12
0.1048	1.003	18.15	72.43	52.82

TABLE 2—SODIUM IODIDE IN ETHYL ALCOHOL

$X \times 10^1$	d_m	M_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.1664	0.8219	47.80	22.32	126.66
0.2038	0.8299	48.18	22.80	126.79
0.2336	0.8362	48.49	22.95	126.91
0.3022	0.8511	49.20	23.40	127.15
0.3766	0.8642	49.98	23.57	127.43

TABLE 3—POTASSIUM ACETATE IN ETHYL ALCOHOL

$X \times 10^1$	M_m	d_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.2317	0.8102	47.28	21.92	126.95
0.2344	0.8108	47.29	21.96	126.95
0.3105	0.8172	47.69	21.63	127.27
0.4355	0.8285	48.34	22.99	127.67
0.5527	0.8397	48.95	23.42	128.20

TABLE 4—*m*-NITRO BENZOIC ACID IN ACETONE

$X \times 10^3$	d_m	M_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.5058	0.8343	63.50	23.77	168.2
0.7883	0.8612	66.63	25.54	173.1
0.8239	0.8678	67.03	25.12	173.7
1.104	0.8982	70.08	27.34	178.4
1.670	0.9368	76.28	28.32	188.0

TABLE 5—ACETONE IN METHYL ALCOHOL

X	d_m	M_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.1802	0.7912	36.68	22.22	100.7
0.2204	0.7921	37.73	22.49	103.7
0.2466	0.7932	38.41	22.89	105.9
0.3674	0.7947	41.54	23.44	115.0

TABLE 6—SALICYLADEHYDE IN CARBON TETRA CHLORIDE

X	d_m	M_m	r_m	$V_m r_m^{1/4}$
0.3848	1.4120	141.6	31.68	237.9
0.3718	1.4160	142.0	31.26	237.2
0.3269	1.4200	143.4	29.41	235.1
0.2467	1.4590	145.9	28.71	231.5
0.1943	1.4850	147.6	28.23	229.1

Discussion and Conclusion

The work was carried out⁵ on about 80 binary systems of various types. In the present paper, however, the representative experimental results on the following typical systems have been given :

- (i) Electrolytes in Water (Table 1)
- (ii) Electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents (Table 2 & 3)

- (iii) Organic solids in organic solvents (Table 4)
- (iv) Organic liquids in organic solvents (Tables 5 & 6)

In each case on plotting $V_m r_m^{1/4}$ values against x straight lines are obtained. Representative plots in the case of aqueous solutions of some electrolytes are given here.

The equation was tested and found to be correct by taking the results of other workers^{4,7-8} also. Using the earlier references, theoretical basis⁹⁻¹⁰ of the equation and its justification from statistical view points¹¹ have already been discussed.^{2,3}

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